

The Succession of Mysticism during the Formative Period of Islamic Reformism

Ishida Yuri (Okayama University)

Today, Muslims consult the descriptions in the Holy Quran and the Hadith, the sayings and deeds of the Prophet Muhammad, as guidelines for their daily lives. The Quran and Hadith have always been respected. Still, their use as legal evidence became common as one of the results of the Islamic reformism that developed in the Arabian Peninsula in the 17th and 18th centuries. It is also known that during this period, the mystic Ibn ‘Arabī (d. 1240) was criticized and replaced by another mystic called al-Ghazālī (d. 1111) [1].

This study aims to clarify the ideological succession of Ibn ‘Arabī and al-Ghazālī based on the Arabic writings of Ja‘far b. Idrīs al-Kattānī [2]. In order to demonstrate his academic legitimacy, al-Kattānī has written down the master-disciple relationships of those who studied the works of Ibn ‘Arabī and al-Ghazālī, all the way back to himself. The information on the master-disciple relationships was collected by reading al-Kattānī’s work and compiled into a list by hand. However, since the section describing the master-disciple relationship is merely a list of names, if we prepare Arabic OCR and NER with sufficient accuracy, it will be possible to automatically collect information from various documents in the future.

Next, the succession of Islamic Mysticism from information on the master-disciple relationship was examined. Figure 1 represents a network created using NodeXL, where people are vertices and interpersonal connections are edges. It is possible to visualize that al-Anṣārī (d. 1520) and al-Kūrānī were people who studied both works of Ibn ‘Arabī and al-Ghazālī. However, based on the year of death, there are 280 years between Ibn ‘Arabī and al-Anṣārī, and 170 years between al-Anṣārī and al-Kūrānī. In the former case, the 280 years are connected by three people, but it should be considered that several people whose names have been forgotten over the long history acted as intermediaries between them. Identifying such gaps in information constitutes a discovery in the study of ideological succession.

Although transforming or coloring the vertices and edges is possible, one simple solution is to introduce a timeline into the network. To depict the succession of the Hadith, Isnalyser [3], a network drawing program with a timeline function, was developed. By setting the timeline interval, it becomes clear where the existence of unmentioned intermediaries should be assumed. Isnalyser will be used to analyze the succession of mysticism during the formation of Islamic reformism, with a focus on information obtained from the work of al-Kattānī.

References

- [1] John O. Voll, "Hadith Scholars and Tariqahs: An Ulama Group in the 18th Century Haramayn and their Impact in the Islamic World," *Journal of Asian and African Studies* 15, no. 3-4: 264–273, 1980.
- [2] Ja‘far b. Idrīs al-Kattānī, *Fahrasa Ja‘far b. Idrīs al-Kattānī*, Muḥammad b. ‘Azūz (ed.), Bayrūt: Dār Ibn Ḥazm, 2004.
- [3] dhakarat, "isnalyser," *GitHub*, 2021. Retrieved on May 7, 2025, from <https://github.com/dhakarat/isnalyserjs>

Figure 1. The Inheritance of Islamic Mysticism Drawn with NodeXL

